

THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE SOVIET AUTHORITY IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS ATTITUDE TO OLD SCHOOLS AND MADRASA

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Annotation:

This article describes the attitude towards old-style schools and madrasahs in the country after the establishment of Soviet power.

Key words: bourgeois revolution, political parties, Muslim, religious schools, Jadid representatives, education, Provisional government, madrasa.

On February 27, 1917, a bourgeois-democratic revolution took place in Petrograd, the capital of the Russian Empire. As a result, the Russian Emperor Nicholas II was overthrown and the rule of the Romanov dynasty, which had ruled for many years, was ended. Two forms of government were formed in the country, that is, the Provisional Government consisting of representatives of the bourgeoisie and the Soviets of Workers' and Peasants' Deputies began to work. The revolution that took place first of all ended the political system of the monarchy and opened doors of opportunity to several sectors of the country. In particular, it is noted that a number of political freedoms were opened to the "Declaration" announced by the Provisional Government, as well as in the "Petition to the citizens of Russia". Freedom of speech and press was established in the country. In particular, an end was put to various religious and national oppressions that existed in the territory of Turkestan during the Russian Empire.

After the Petrograd events, a new government was established in the country, and steps were taken towards democracy and social justice. The majority of the country's population, its many peoples, various classes, social groups, political parties and social movements accepted the revolution with high spirits and supported it.

The February Revolution had a positive impact on the lives of Muslim clerics. Their previously high positions began to be restored. At the same time, schools and madrassas in the country began to recover their position. Despite many restrictions and restrictions during the empire, they maintained their reputation among the population. Local youths have shown a high initiative for the inclusion of secular sciences in the curricula of schools and madrasahs.

Especially Munavvar Qori, a great fighter and skilled pedagogue Abdurashidkhanov's services in this work were great. At the beginning of the 20th century, the Jadidism movement, which was widely formed in Turkestan, made a great contribution to the enlightenment of the local population. Jadids united Muslim priests, teachers and students of religious schools in their ranks. Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Qadiri, Ubaydulla Khojayev, Polvonniyoz Haji Yusupov, Tavallo, Cholpon were among the brightest representatives of the Jadids.

Jadid enlighteners began to protect the political interests of local peoples in direct democratic processes that began after February 1917. They are determined to strengthen national unity and cohesion in the country and to develop and promote national culture and education, which is the first task of any country. On the initiative of Jadids, organizations such as "Shurai Islamiya", "Shurai Ulamo", "Ittihodi Taraqqi", "Turon", "Milliy Ittikhod", "Milliy Istiqlal" were established. The main goal and main idea of most of these organizations was to establish national, cultural freedom and democratic principles in the country.

Jadid representatives began to publish newspapers and magazines in many cities of Turkestan in order to raise the political consciousness of the local population. In particular, press publications such as "Khurshid", "Sadoi Turkistan", "Turk eli", "Najot", "Kengash", "Shuroi Islam" were published in Tashkent.

Democratic processes in February 1917 also covered Turkestan. These processes especially affected the field of national education. Because even in these times, there were schools, convents, and madrasahs that were deeply rooted in the cultural life of the country. Together with these schools, Russian-style schools and new-style schools operated in the country.

The congress held in Skobelev (New Margilon) on July 14, 1917 plays an important role in the implementation of democratic changes in Turkestan. The autonomy project was discussed there. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov and others took part in the development of the "Autonomy Project". In this document, religious issues, including school and special attention was paid to the issue of madrasahs. In order to control religious matters in the country, they suggested establishing a special "Mahkamai Shar'iyah" (Chamber of Laws) in the capital, its departments in the regions, and courthouses in every city and village. In addition, along with secular education, a wide path has been opened to the activities of religious educational institutions.

In 1917, the issue of establishing a national education system in Turkestan was one of the problems that had to be solved. On May 9-14, the 1st national congress of teachers took place in Tashkent. He discussed many issues related to the state of the education system and established the "Teachers' Union of Turkistan". S. Maqsudov, a member of the Turkestan Committee of the Provisional Government, L.Zimin, a major orientalist, F.Yegorov, an educational inspector of the Ferghana region, who spoke at the congress, proved that the Russian-system schools are useless for the education of the local population. they gave.

Also, a special place was allocated to the activities of old schools and madrassas at the congress. Based on the decision issued at the congress, it was determined that all madrasahs in the country should be divided into three levels: lower (adno), middle (avsat), upper (excellent) level. Unlike in the previous times, the educational work in madrasahs was transferred directly to the board of teachers. According to the decision of the parliament, the supervision of the work of madrasahs belongs to the religious administration. On September 10, 1917, the Tashkent City Duma approved the project to transform Russian-style schools into national schools. At the same time, the Duma made a decision to open 12 traditional schools at the expense of state funds. However, the possibilities of development of the traditional schools of Turkestan after February 1917 were not realized as a result of the coup d'état carried out by the Bolsheviks in October.

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